

"REVOLUTIONIZING AGRICULTURAL EXPORT: A CENTRALIZED DIGITAL PLATFORM FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT"

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Abstract. The provided text discusses the significance of information technologies, particularly GIS, in the context of agricultural management. It emphasizes the role of a three-tier architecture, based on Open Source technology and utilizing ExtJS, in developing a web-based GIS application called Agrifootprint. The annotation highlights the importance of cost-effective solutions, scalability, and ease of maintenance in achieving enhanced agricultural productivity and competitiveness. The integrated system aims to facilitate informed decision-making for farmers by efficiently managing georeferenced data and providing valuable insights into factors such as crop yield estimates, soil analysis, and resource optimization.

Keywords: Information Technologies, Information Society, Technological Paradigm, Geospatial Management, Agricultural Information Systems, Agricultural Productivity, GIS, Web-based GIS, Three-tier Architecture, Open Source Technology, ExtJS, Scalability, Ease of Maintenance, Decision-making, Agrifootprint, Interoperability, Sustainability.

The processes for access and use of information and technology by individuals and organizations as a whole constitute the Information Technologies and define the ain foundations of what is currently named the Information Society Castells points out that we are in a society whose economy is dominated by a technological paradigm in which information is its raw material. That is, the

information is critical to the day-to-day organization of all the different tasks that constitute their work processes. It is expected that a relationship exists between the effective management of organizations and how they treat and manage information. Goncalves states that people, information and knowledge are key assets that differentiate organizations, and success is increasingly the result of the ability of its management. Find the best ways to do this management requires a proactive and persistent attitude in the pursuit of improving posture, which includes having openness to innovate. Information technologies has been of utmost importance in Geospatial management. In the last years we've seen the growth of a special relevance to the agricultural Information systems. This importance is reflected in the implementation of systems for the processing and handling of agricultural land and products and the use of information systems to influence agricultural productivity. It can help to take better decisions regarding land, labor, livestock, capital and management. Agricultural productivity can undoubtedly be improved by relevant, reliable and useful data, information and knowledge. Hence, the creation of agricultural information (by extension services, research, education plans and others) is now often managed by agricultural organizations that create information systems to disseminate information to farmers so that farmers can make better decisions in order to take advantage of market opportunities and manage continuous changes in their production systems.

In this article, in a more limited aspect, we describe the implementation of an innovative system architecture for the management of agricultural properties which allows a more agile and efficient land and crop management, aiming towards an enhanced productivity and competitiveness. Since making decisions based on geography is basic to human thinking, GIS could be defined as a technological tool for comprehending geography and making intelligent decisions based on space and location, by handling and addressing the “where” type of questions about spatial phenomena. GIS, has been around before the Internet, and

can be described as a system of hardware, software, and procedures that capture, store, edit, manipulate, manage, analyze, share and display georeferenced data.

From routinely performing work-related tasks to scientifically exploring the complexities of our world, GIS gives people the geographic advantage to become more productive, more aware, and more responsive citizens.

Nowadays, GIS are playing an increasing role in agriculture production throughout the world by helping farmers increase production, reduce costs, and manage their land more efficiently. While natural inputs in farming cannot be controlled, they can be better understood and managed with GIS applications such as crop yield estimates, soil amendment analyses, erosion identification and remediation, predict outcomes and improve business practices. GIS applications is also useful in agriculture, since it can reduce farm input costs, such as fertilizer, fuel, seed, labor and transportations, additionally, farm managers can use GIS to submit government program applications, simplifying what used to be time-consuming multistep processes. As stated before, the main goal of the Agrifootprint system was to develop and implement a Web-based Geographic Information System with a custom-made, comprehensive and user-friendly geospatial system, in order to integrate and manage data from several small agriculture enterprises.

During the first steps of the development process of the application, the team executed a system analysis and requirements, according to the client everyday needs. To pursue this goal the team promoted an assessment, with interviews, in order to review the client's specifications, and also to specify the system in terms of its strategic objectives and required functionalities, design and usability. The implemented system architecturen it's a typical three tier architecture, entirely based on Open Source technology, and therefore does not involve licensing costs, which is an enormous advantage, since it cuts off the cost for payment of annual licensing. This Open Source solution still allows the

development and deployment of a truly interoperable and fully functional web-based GIS application. WebGIS systems usually present a multi-tier client-server architecture in which data presentation, processing and storage are logically separated processes. This type of architecture allows a greater system modularity in which several software components are selected developed according to the inherent needs of a specific tier and, therefore, improve the overall maintainability and sustainability of the system. For such reasons, the implemented system architecture is based upon a 3-tier client-server architecture. Moreover, only Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) was considered when selecting the different components to fulfil each tier with the necessary functionalities.

We've chosen ExtJS for its structure and consistency, as it considerably improves scalability and ease of maintenance of the application, backed up by a solid architecture. The best way is to follow certain conventions and define application views, models and controllers before actually implementing them.

Forms, tables, charts, map panels and basically every other interface element are placed on different views. The model can be considered a runtime repository, managing the data structures that are accessed by the views. ExtJS also packs a Store class that encapsulates a client side cache of Model objects. Stores load data via Proxy, and also provide functions for sorting, filtering and querying the model instances contained within it. Ultimately, the controller is the logical decision point that will retrieve, build or modify a Model based on the required action. It is also possible to handle triggered events that comes from the views. Multiple models and views can be connected to one or several controllers. In Agrifootprint's case, the latter is used to manage requests between the web application and the server.

In conclusion, the text underscores the pivotal role of information technologies, specifically GIS and a three-tier architecture, in revolutionizing agricultural management through systems like Agrifootprint. By leveraging Open

Source technology and the ExtJS framework, the implemented web-based GIS application offers cost-effective, scalable, and easily maintainable solutions. The focus on georeferenced data enables farmers to make informed decisions, optimize resources, and enhance overall productivity in the agricultural sector. The conclusion highlights the importance of technological innovation and strategic information management in addressing the dynamic challenges of modern agriculture.